

A multivariate approach to estimate design loads for offshore wind turbines.

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Abstract

The design of offshore wind farms is a complex process which requires a detailed study of the oceanographic, meteorological and geotechnical conditions at the site. The structure and all structural members shall be designed in a way that they can be resistant against different kind of loads: permanent, variable, environmental, accidental and deformations. This paper is focused on those called environmental loads. The main environmental conditions which may contribute to structural damage, operational disturbances or other failures are: wind, waves, currents and sea ice. Thus, the combination of the different parameters may produce many different critical situations for the integrity of the structure, requiring the calculation of long time series corresponding to long term historical data situations. The most accurate techniques available at the moment to estimate loads acting upon a structure are numerical and physical models, however they are very time-consuming and the calculation of long time series of data is unfeasible. Therefore, a new hybrid methodology to select waves-wind-current representative conditions that allow the interpolation of long time series of forces on a wind turbine is proposed. The methodology consists of a selection of a subset of representative cases of wave-wind-current climate at the structure's location using a maximum dissimilarity algorithm, then estimating loads acting upon the structure for the sea-wind states selected and the

reconstruction of loads corresponding to historical data using an interpolation technique based on radial basis function. To validate the proposed methodology and because of there is no availability of long time records of loads on wind turbines, the well-known IEC 61400-3 has been applied to estimate the loads for the complete reanalysis time series of waves, winds and currents. The validation of the results confirms the ability of the methodology developed to reconstruct time series of forces on the structure based on the previously selected cases. This methodology permits application of numerical and physical models to offshore wind farm design, considerably reducing the number of tests or simulations.

Keywords

Offshore wind farms, environmental forces, long-term distribution, maximum dissimilarity algorithm, reanalysis database.

1. INTRODUCTION

The need for clean, renewable and sustainable energy sources has increased in recent decades. Along with this need comes the development of technology and the capabilities of human society. As a result of these two ideas, offshore wind energy appears. Wind energy is one of the most promising options for electricity generation. According to the Europe 2020 Renewable Energy Targets, wind energy installed production will increase from 2.9 GW in 2010 to 40GW in 2020.

Technology today makes offshore structures possible where conditions are favourable. A good example is seen on the North West Europe coast, especially the North Sea, where the 2020 installed production target is 25GW. There, continental shelf conditions allow good foundations for turbines on the sea floor, and the constant winds provide the energy needed to start the process. On the Spanish coast, the Mediterranean would be where it would be

possible to install wind farms moored to the sea bottom. The Atlantic Coast and the Canary Islands Coasts are too deep for that.

The analysis and design of offshore wind farms is a complex process that involves many technical requirements. This design has to guarantee safe and economical operation during the service life of at least 20 years, and must take account of the most important external conditions, closely related to the wind farm location.

According to the DNV-OS-J101 Offshore Standards, when designing wind turbine farms a high number of load cases should be considered. These load cases fall into different categories: Permanent (mass), Variable (actuation, operational), Environmental (wind, waves, current, ice), Accidental (collisions, explosions, fire, etc.) and Deformation loads (temperature, built-in deformations and settlement of foundations). This study is focused on Environmental applied loads (wind, wave and currents) during the operational life of the wind turbine. Other kind of loads (for example: accidental loads, internal loads due to the dynamic response of the structure, loads associated with turbine or grid faults,...) are not considered.

For offshore structures, environmental load involves loads due to waves, wind, current, earthquakes, ice, snow, tidal, scouring, etc., but the most important are those related to waves, winds and currents. From all the external agents referred to before, the design rules establish multiple combinations of situations that may occur during the lifecycle of the structure to be studied and/or simulated, both numerically and physically. In terms of numerical models, several computer programs have been developed to simulate the behaviour of offshore structures (SACS, ANSYS-ASAS OFFSHORE, STAAD PRO). Related to these aero-hydro-servo-elastic time-domain simulations have appeared in the last years the contour line or surface methods, which can be very useful in terms of extreme responses for limits states designs (Karimirad and Moan 2011; Karimirad and Moan 2012);

but the assessment of combined wave, wind and current loads on offshore structures continues to be a time-consuming process. On the other hand, physical models give good results, but the number of cases that can be tested is limited by financial and time factors. Despite their limitations, physical models are very useful for optimizing design and for the verification and validation of numerical models.

This study proposes a hybrid methodology to obtain long time series of environmental loads on an offshore wind turbine by simulating a limited number of sea-wind states. The methodology is based on that proposed to downscale wave dynamics in coastal structures (Guanche et al., 2011) and combines a selection of sea-wind states using data mining algorithms and a later reconstruction interpolation with radial basis functions (RBF). To validate the proposed methodology the loads have been estimated applying IEC 61400-3 (2009), but the final objective of the proposed methodology is to apply numerical or physical models. It must be noted that some simplifications have been made when estimating the loads.

Using this methodology, the number of numerical simulations or physical tests needed to reproduce long time series of loads on the wind turbine can be reduced. The availability of long time series of loads on the wind turbine gives access to all the combinations of effects due to external agents that may not be included in the recommended load cases of the standards. This study therefore aims to provide a useful tool in wind turbine structure design.

This paper is organized as follows: an introduction to the problem and the different solutions available are explained in the first Section. In Section 2 the proposed methodology is described. Sections 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 respectively explain: the database used, the selection of wind-sea states, the calculation of the environmental loads on the wind turbine, time series reconstruction and validation. In Section 8, design tools are developed using the proposed methodology. Finally, the conclusions of the study are set out in Section 9.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology proposed is a transformation to design parameters (loads) of a representative subset of sea and wind conditions from a historical database, and a statistical reconstruction of the time series of the parameters calculated (Camus et al., 2011). The stages of the methodology are the following: (1) definition of the met-ocean database (2) selection of representative wind and sea states using data mining algorithms; (3) loads on a wind turbine calculation; (4) transference of the complete series of wind and sea states using an interpolation scheme. The proposed methodology has been successfully used to study loads acting upon vertical breakwaters (Guanche et al 2011). A diagram of the methodology is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of the methodology

(1) Use of this methodology requires a long-term database (N data) of the different variables involved at the location. For this application, the number of independent met-ocean parameters is $n=8$. These variables define the characteristics of waves (significant wave height (H_s), wave period (T_m), wave direction (θ_{Waves})), wind (magnitude and direction (V_{1-hour} , θ_{Wind})), currents (the speed and direction of the tidal current (U_{Tidal} , θ_{Tidal})) and sea level (SWL).

(2) The aim of the selection process was to extract a representative subset of wind-wave conditions of the long time series from reanalysis databases. The Maximum Dissimilarity Algorithm (MDA) allows an automatic selection of a subset of sea states which are representative of met-ocean climate at the location useful to be combined with an interpolation technique (Camus, 2011 b).

These reanalysis data are defined by scalar and directional parameters of different magnitudes which require normalization and an implementation of the distance in the circle for the directional parameter in the MDA algorithm. The scalar variables are normalized by scaling the variable values between 0 and 1 with a simple linear transformation requiring two parameters, the minimum and maximum value of the two scalar variables. In the case of circular variables (defined in radians or in sexagesimal degrees using the scaling factor $\pi/180$), and considering that the maximum difference between two directions over the circle equals π and the minimum difference equals 0, normalization was achieved by dividing the direction values by π . In this way, the circular distance was rescaled between 0 and 1.

The initial data of the subset $\{D_1\}$ was considered to be the sea state with the highest significant wave height. The rest of the $M-1$ elements were selected iteratively, transferring the most dissimilar ones to the subset established by the MaxMin version of the algorithm (Willet, 1996). This dissimilarity was determined using the Euclidean Circular Distance (EC distance). Finally, we de-normalized the subset applying the opposite transformation used during normalization.

(3) In this phase of the methodology, loads were calculated for each of the selected sea-wind conditions at the structure's location. A simplified method (based on IEC 61400-3) is considered because it allows the direct transformation of the long-time hourly reanalysis series (20 years for this application) which made the validation of the proposed methodology possible.

(4) The reconstruction of the time series of loads on the wind turbine used an interpolation technique based on radial basis function (RBF), a very handy method for scattered and multivariate data (Franke, 1982, and Hardy, 1971).

Figure 2 shows a detailed schematic diagram of the methodology.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the methodology proposed

An application is considered to explain the proposed methodology. The offshore wind turbine under study is located on the north-east Mediterranean coast of Spain between the city of Tarragona and the Ebro River Delta. This place was chosen because the continental shelf in the area would, as already pointed out, allow an offshore wind farm to be located there.

Figure 3 shows the location of the case study.

Figure 3. Location of the case study.

3. DATABASE

To apply the methodology described, long-term database of waves, currents and winds from the location are needed.

The parameters were taken from reanalysis databases due to its adequate length, covering 20 years (1989-2009). The wave data were taken from DOW 2.1 (Downscaled Ocean Waves), a coastal hourly wave reanalysis database with a spatial resolution of 0.125° in the western Mediterranean Sea. This database has been obtained downscaling the GOW 2.1 database applying an hybrid methodology (Camus, 2011 b) which combines the SWAN wave model (dynamical downscaling) with statistical tools (MDA algorithm for the selection of 500 representative deep water conditions and RBF interpolation technique for the 20-year hourly time series reconstruction). GOW 2.1 (Global Ocean Waves 2.1, IH Cantabria) is a wave reanalysis database generated using WW3 model and forced by 15-km resolution wind fields from a dynamic downscaling (WRF model) nested to ERA-Interim (1989-2009) atmospheric reanalysis.

The wind data were extracted from the SeaWind-ERA-INTERIM database (IH Cantabria) (Menendez et al. 2011). SeaWind constitutes an hourly wind reanalysis database on a 15 km spatial resolution grid, which provides surface winds at a height of 10 meters. It was generated by dynamic downscaling, using the WRF model from a global reanalysis (ERA-Interim, developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)) over the South Atlantic-European region and the Mediterranean basin.

The storm surge data used were extracted from the GOS 2.1 database (Global Ocean Surges 2.1, IH Cantabria), (Abascal et al. 2011), a high-resolution hourly storm surge reanalysis database covering 20 years (1898-2009) in Southern Europe, with a spatial resolution of $1/8^\circ$ (~13 km). It was generated with the 3D ROMS model (Regional Ocean Modelling System) developed by the Rutgers Ocean Modelling Group and forced with high-resolution wind and pressure data (~15 km) from a dynamic downscaling of ERA-INTERIM.

4. SELECTION OF WIND AND SEA STATES

The subset is selected using the maximum-dissimilarity algorithm (MDA). Figure 4 shows the resulting clusters or selected data when applying three different data mining techniques: KMA (K-means algorithm), self-organizing maps (SOM) and MDA, in a data sample located in a circle domain (Camus, 2011a). It can be observed that MDA distributes selected data rather evenly across the space, with some points selected in the outline of the data space, guarantee the most representative subset from the original sample.

Figure 4. Comparison of KMA (k-means), SOM (Self-Organizing Maps) and MDA (Maximum dissimilarity) algorithms

Therefore, selection was done using this technique because of its ability to fairly represent the space with some points selected in the outline of the data set. An explanation of the algorithm and the required data pre-processes is given in Appendix 1. Different selections have been performed using MDA for different subset sizes. Figure 5 shows the long-time series of the 8 independent variables with the data selected by MDA algorithm. Figure 5 shows the long-time series of the 8 independent variables with the data selected by MDA algorithm.

Figure 5. Time series of H_s , T_p , θ (wave direction), SWL, Tidal Current (in its components X and Y) and Wind (in its components X and Y) at the wind turbine location (grey line), the cases selected by MDA algorithm, $M=1,50$ red points, $M=51,100$ green points and $M=101,200$ yellow points.

Figure 6 shows different scatter plots of the hourly time series, and the data selected in different colors ($M=1,50$ in red, $M=51,100$ in green and $M=101,200$ in yellow). The cases selected span the space of the input data, trying to cover it evenly and fill it uniformly. It must be mentioned that the MDA algorithm is a deterministic method, so for example in a subset of $M=200$ cases, the first 100 will be the same as those for a subset of $M=100$ cases.

Figure 6. Distribution of cases selected by MDA algorithm ($M=1,50$ red points, $M=51,100$ green points and $M=101,200$ yellow points).

5. CALCULATION OF WIND TURBINE LOADS

IEC 61400 (2009) is a class of IEC international standards for wind turbines. Subclass 61400-3 refers to design requirements for offshore wind turbines, explaining how to study

the structural components in order to provide an appropriate level of protection against damage from all hazards during the planned lifetime. The most important environmental loads on a monopile offshore wind turbine can be divided into the forces due to wind, waves and currents as shown in Figure 7. These forces arise as a function of different parameters. The momentum calculation follows the same scheme. All moments are referred to the bottom of the sea:

$$\vec{F} = \vec{F}_{Waves-Current} + \vec{F}_{Wind} \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{M} = \vec{M}_{Waves-Current} + \vec{M}_{Wind} \quad (2)$$

Figure 7. Loads on a wind turbine

Wave-Current Forces

Particle velocities due to waves depend on H_s , T_p , θ_{Waves} and SWL. There are many ways to attempt to describe the velocity and acceleration profile. For this study in the interest of simplicity, linear wave theory was used despite not being the most accurate method taking into account the largest waves in water depths typical for offshore wind farms.

$$\vec{W}(z,t) = \pm \frac{H}{2} \cdot \frac{2\pi}{T_m} \cdot \frac{\cosh(k(h+z))}{\sinh kh} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T_m} \cdot t\right) \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{\dot{W}}(z,t) = \pm \frac{H}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{2\pi}{T_m}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{\cosh(k(h+z))}{\sinh kh} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T_m} \cdot t\right) \quad (4)$$

As seen, due to water oscillation movement velocities are time-dependent on the wave period. Therefore, there are both a positive and a negative component inside the same wave. In this way, the highest wave ($H_{max}=1.8H_s$) with the mean period (T_m) of each sea state was chosen, and maximum velocity instant was taken from its period.

When there is a current the velocity profile given by it can be assumed to be described by:

$$\vec{U}(z)_{Tidal} = \left| \vec{U}(z)_{Tidal} \right| \cdot \left[\frac{z+h}{h} \right]^{1/7} (\sin \theta_{Tide} \vec{i} + \cos \theta_{Tide} \vec{j}) \quad (5)$$

$$\vec{U}(z)_{Wind} = 0.01 \cdot \vec{V}_{1-hour}(z=10m) \cdot \left[\frac{z+20}{20} \right] (\sin \theta_{Wind} \vec{i} + \cos \theta_{Wind} \vec{j}) \quad (6)$$

For collinear waves and currents, velocities profiles (waves and current in the wave direction component) should be added before estimating forces to take into account wave-current interaction. So, the hydrodynamic forces (wave-current) are calculated with:

$$\vec{F}_{WC_{\theta_w}}(t) = \int_{z=-h}^{z=0} \left\{ \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot C_d \cdot \rho_{water} \cdot D \cdot \left| \vec{W}(z,t) + \vec{U}_{\theta_w}(z) \right| \cdot \left(\vec{W}(z,t) + \vec{U}_{\theta_w}(z) \right) \right] + \left[\frac{\pi}{4} \cdot C_M \cdot \rho_{water} \cdot D^2 \cdot \dot{\vec{W}}(z,t) + \dot{\vec{U}}_{\theta_w}(z) \right] \right\} dz \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{F}_{WC_{\theta_w}} = \max \left\{ \vec{F}_{WC_{\theta_w}}(t) \right\} \cdot (\sin \theta_{Waves} \vec{i} + \cos \theta_{Waves} \vec{j}) \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{M}_{WC_{\theta_w}}(t) = \int_{z=-h}^{z=0} \left\{ \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot C_d \cdot \rho_{water} \cdot D \cdot \left| \vec{W}(z,t) + \vec{U}_{\theta_w}(z) \right| \cdot \left(\vec{W}(z,t) + \vec{U}_{\theta_w}(z) \right) \right] + \left[\frac{\pi}{4} \cdot C_M \cdot \rho_{water} \cdot D^2 \cdot \dot{\vec{W}}(z,t) + \dot{\vec{U}}_{\theta_w}(z) \right] \right\} \cdot (z+h) \cdot dz \quad (9)$$

$$\vec{M}_{WC_{\theta_w}} = \max \left\{ \vec{M}_{WC_{\theta_w}}(t) \right\} \cdot (\sin \theta_{Waves} \vec{i} + \cos \theta_{Waves} \vec{j}) \quad (10)$$

The non-collinear component of the current with the wave direction (current orthogonal to the wave direction) contributes with a drag force calculated by:

$$\vec{F}_{WC_{\perp \theta_w}} = \int_{z=-h}^{z=0} \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_d \cdot \rho_{water} \cdot D \cdot \left| \vec{U}_{\perp \theta_w}(z)_{Tidal} \right| \cdot \vec{U}_{\perp \theta_w}(z)_{Tidal} \cdot dz \quad (11)$$

$$\vec{M}_{WC_{\perp \theta_w}} = \int_{z=-h}^{z=0} \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_d \cdot \rho_{water} \cdot D \cdot \left| \vec{U}_{\perp \theta_w}(z)_{Tidal} \right| \cdot \vec{U}_{\perp \theta_w}(z)_{Tidal} \cdot (z+h) \cdot dz \quad (12)$$

Wind Forces

Finally, forces due to wind are a function of V_{1-hour} , θ_{Wind} and SWL, and can be divided into the forces acting on the tower of the turbine and those acting on the wind turbine. For

this particular application, forces and moments on the tower are calculated using the IEC standards (IEC, 61400-3, 2009) and those on the turbine are calculated on the assumption of a 5 MW Reference turbine as defined by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (Jonkman, J. et al. 2009.). Nevertheless, the methodology proposed allows use of sophisticated numerical models. The cut-of velocity was set at 25 m/s, so with wind speeds above that value the force on the turbine is assumed to be 0. Figure 8 shows the thrust force applied on the wind turbine related to wind speed.

$$\vec{F}_{Wind} = \vec{F}_{VTower} + \vec{F}_{VTurbine} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \vec{F}_{VTower} = \int_{z=0-SWL}^{z=nacelle} \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_d \cdot \rho_{air} \cdot D \cdot |\vec{V}_{1-hour}(z)| \cdot \vec{V}_{1-hour}(z) \cdot dz \quad (13) \\ \vec{F}_{VTurbine} \rightarrow \text{NREL /TP-500-38060} \quad (14) \\ \vec{F}_{VTurbine} \rightarrow \text{NREL /TP-500-38060} \quad (15) \end{array} \right.$$

$$\vec{M}_{Wind} = \vec{M}_{VTower} + \vec{M}_{VTurbine} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \vec{M}_{VTower} = \int_{z=0-SWL}^{z=nacelle} \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_d \cdot \rho_{air} \cdot D \cdot |\vec{V}_{1-hour}(z)| \cdot \vec{V}_{1-hour}(z) \cdot (z+d) dz \quad (16) \\ \vec{M}_{VTurbine} = F_{VTurbine} \cdot z \quad (17) \\ \vec{M}_{VTurbine} = F_{VTurbine} \cdot z \quad (18) \end{array} \right.$$

where:

$$\vec{V}_{1-hour}(z) = \vec{V}_{1-hour}(z=10m) \cdot \left(\frac{z}{10} \right)^{0.14} \cdot (\sin \theta_{Waves} \vec{i} + \cos \theta_{Waves} \vec{j}) \quad (19)$$

Figure 8. Thrust force on the turbine

6. TIME SERIES RECONSTRUCTION

The reconstruction of the time series of loads on the wind turbine used an interpolation technique based on radial basis function (RBF), a very useful scheme for scattered and multivariate data. The RBF approximation has been successfully applied in many fields, usually with better results than other interpolation methods.

This interpolation method consists of approximating the real-valued function $f=f(x)$ with a weighted sum of radially symmetric basic function located at the scattered data points $\{x_1, \dots, x_M\}$ where the associated real function values $\{f_1, \dots, f_M\}$ are available. Therefore, after calculating the forces indicated in section 5 for the M select waves-wind-current conditions, functions for the total horizontal and vertical force (F_u, F_v) and for the horizontal and vertical momentum (M_u, M_v) are determined using RBF method. The 20-year time series of these forces and momentums can be reconstructed applying the corresponding RBF functions in the rest of the environmental conditions. A detail explanation can be found in Appendix2.

7. VALIDATION

To evaluate the progression of the accuracy in the reconstructed time series of the parameters calculated $\{F_u\}$, $\{F_v\}$, $\{M_u\}$ and $\{M_v\}$ (horizontal and vertical forces and momentums respectively) they were reconstructed considering different numbers of cases selected by the MDA algorithm ($M=10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 300, 500, 750$ and 1000).

On the other hand, the values for the same four parameters ($\{F_u\}$, $\{F_v\}$, $\{M_u\}$ and $\{M_v\}$) for the entire 20 year time series were calculated analytically. Thus in this application, we have the real values available for the validation of the reconstructed time series using the proposed methodology.

The scatter plots for the propagated time series and the reconstructed time series for F_u and F_v are shown in Figure 9. The reconstructed time series with $M=75, 200, 500$ and 1000 selected cases are shown in the subplots. The normalized root mean square error ($NRMSE$) and the correlation coefficient (ρ) were computed for F_u and F_v . These statistics are given on table

1.

Figure 9. Scatter plot of the time series (calculated vs. reconstructed) of F_u (X component) and F_v (Y component) considering $M=75$, $M=200$ and $M=1000$

Table 1. The normalized root mean square error and the correlation coefficient of F_u (X component) and F_v (Y component)

It can be seen that, with the proposed methodology, the reconstructed time series are more accurate when using more cases in the calculation of the corresponding RBF function. The differences between the calculated and the reconstructed time series are more significant using $M=75$ cases. However, the increased accuracy of reconstruction is not so great when using $M=500$ cases or $M=1000$ cases.

The reconstructed time series of F_u and F_v using $M=200$ cases (in orange), $M=1000$ cases (in red) and the real-time series (in black) are shown in Figure 10, demonstrating that the proposed methodology is able to reproduce the structure of the time series.

Figure 10. Time series calculated (in black) and the time series reconstructed considering $M=200$ cases (in orange) and $M=1000$ cases (in red) of parameters F_u (X component) and F_v (Y component)

8. DESIGN TOOLS

The availability of long time series of environmental forces acting on a wind turbine could become a useful tool in offshore wind turbine design and would allow analysis of critical structural integrity situations representing an improvement in the design of offshore wind turbine farms. Moreover, this study might be understood from different points of view. The data used are the reconstructed series based on $MDA=1000$ selected cases.

In terms of extreme situations, Figure 11 shows a Peak Over Threshold (POT) distribution of the environmental forces acting upon the wind turbine, with a threshold at the 99.5 percentile.

Figure 11. Peak Over Threshold (POT) distribution of the module of forces at the wind turbine (95% confidence intervals in dashed lines)

Figure 12 shows the rose directional distribution of probabilities for the wind (upper left rose), wave (upper central rose), currents (upper right rose) and total force (lower rose). However, figure 13 shows wind, waves and currents contribution only during 1992. Moreover, figure 14 shows the spatial total force distribution during 1999 (left side rose), 2000 (central rose) and 2001 (right side rose).

Figure 12. Roses of spatial distribution of wind (upper left rose), wave (upper central rose), currents (upper right rose) and total force magnitude (lower rose)

The methodology proposed also allows the availability of long-term series for the different components of the environmental forces on the monopile, and so may be made a spatial and/or temporal study depending on the components. Figure 13 shows the probabilistic roses of the three main components (waves, wind and currents) and the total force for a period of only one year (1992). It can be seen that in that year (1992) the worst states are due to waves, but that the most common state arises from the combination of waves and the main wind direction. Notice that the forces are misaligned, so that induced movements should be carefully studied to avoid fatigue problems. At this case study location, current forces are

negligible compared with waves or wind, but at other location they may become a significant force. The inclusion of current forces in the proposed methodology makes it more versatile.

Figure 13. Probabilistic roses of the different components of forces acting on a wind turbine, 1992 (wind component: left panel, hydrodynamic component: central panel and total force (sum of both components): right panel).

But not only the spatial distributions of force components are important when designing wind turbine farms. Temporary variations of the spatial distributions of total forces are also very important, and their study calls for long-term series. Figure 14 shows the spatial total forces distribution acting on the wind turbine over three consecutive years (1999 left side rose, 2000 central rose and 2001 right side rose). The variation in the shape and magnitude of the cluster of dots is clear.

Figure 14. Probabilistic roses for the total force acting upon a wind turbine, 1999 (left panel), 2000 (central panel) and 2001(right panel)

Figures 11 to 14 serve as examples of the analysis that can be made with the availability of long time series of forces, and also the combination of their different components. Thus, the availability of long time load series for a wind turbine seems to be useful, taking account of some combinations of external agents (waves, wind, currents) that may not be included in the load cases proposed by the standards.

9. CONCLUSIONS

In this study a hybrid methodology has been developed to obtain long time series of the environmental loads on an offshore wind turbine, using some simplifications that drastically reduce the computational effort. These loads can be determined by numerical models or semi-empirical formulations. The methodology is based on a selection of representative sea-wind states at the turbine location, calculation of the dynamic loads corresponding to these selected sea-wind states and a multidimensional RBF interpolation to reconstruct the long time series of dynamic loads.

The availability of long time series of the loads acting on an offshore wind turbine allows the analysis of critical stability situations, representing an improvement in their design. Nevertheless, this methodology can be also applied to reconstruct other parameters involved in offshore structure design and also allows the inclusion of more variables that may influence the process.

To analyze possible application of the proposed methodology to real cases, an application at a specific location is presented. Moreover, some examples of design tools extracted from the results obtained are described.

APPENDIX 1. Maximum Dissimilarity Algorithm (MDA).

In the development of computer-based methods for selecting sets of structurally diverse compounds from chemical databases, dissimilarity-based compound selection has been suggested as an effective method for identify a subset comprising the most dissimilar data in a database (Snarey et al., 1997). The maximum-dissimilarity algorithm (MDA) is one subclass of these selection techniques. The selection process starts initializing the subset by transferring one vector from the data sample. The remaining elements are selected iteratively, calculating the

dissimilarity between each remaining data in the database and the elements of the subset, and transferring the most dissimilar one to the subset.

In this work, data sample $X_i = \{H_{si}, T_{mi}, SWL_i, \theta_{Waves\ i}, U_{Tidal\ i}, \theta_{Tidal\ i}, V_{1-hour\ i}, \theta_{Windi}\}$; $i=1, \dots, N$ are defined by scalar and directional variables of different magnitudes. The vector components require to be normalized in order to be equally weighted in the similarity criterion. The scalar variables are normalized by scaling the variables values between [0,1] with a simple linear transformation, which requires two parameters, the minimum and maximum value of the two scalar variables. The circular variables are normalized by dividing the direction values between π , therefore rescaling the circular distance, which could be maximum equal to π , between [0,1]. The Euclidean-circular distance is implemented in the similarity criterion.

Between all the algorithm variants (Willet et al., 1996), the MaxMin version has been considered in order to obtain the most representative subset of the diversity of the data. For example, if the subset is formed by R ($R \leq M$) vectors, the dissimilarity between the vector i of the data sample $N-R$ and the j vectors belonging to the R subset is calculated:

$$d_{ij} = \|X_i - D_j\|; i = 1, \dots, N - R; j = 1, \dots, R \quad (\text{A1.1})$$

Subsequently, the dissimilarity $d_{i,subset}$ between the vector i and the subset R , is calculated as:

$$d_{i,subset} = \min \left\{ \|X_i - D_j\| \right\}; i = 1, \dots, N - R; j = 1, \dots, R \quad (\text{A1.2})$$

Once the $N-R$ dissimilarities are calculated, the next selected data is the one with the largest value of $d_{i,subset}$. Moreover, the efficient algorithm developed by Polinsky et al. (1996) has been implemented which implies not calculating the distance between the different vectors d_{ij} in the definition of the distance $d_{i,subset}$. For example, in the selection of the R vector, the

distance $d_{i,subset}$ is defined as the minimum distance between the vector i of the data sample (consisting of $N-(R-1)$ vectors at this cycle) and the last vector transferred to the subset R , and the minimum distance between the vector i and the $R-1$ vectors of the subset determined in the previous cycle:

$$d_{i,subset}^{\min} = \min \left[d_{i,R}, d_{i,subset(R-1)}^{\min} \right] \quad (\text{A1.3})$$

After, finishing the selection process, a denormalization of the subset have to be done. Finally, the MDA subset is defined by $D_i = \{H_{si}, T_{mi}, SWL_i, \theta_{Waves\ i}, U_{Tidal\ i}, \theta_{Tidal\ i}, V_{1-hour\ i}, \theta_{Wind\ i}\}$; $j=1, \dots, M$.

APPENDIX 2. Radial Basis Function (RBF) Interpolation Technique.

Suppose that $f=f(x)$ is the real-valued function that we want to approximate. We are given M scattered data points $\{x_1, \dots, x_M\}$ of dimension n and the associated real function values $\{f_1, \dots, f_M\}$, being $f_i=f(x_j)$, $j=1, \dots, M$. The RBF interpolation method consists of a weighted sum of radially symmetric basic function located in the data points. The approximation function is assumed to be of the form:

$$RBF(x) = p(x) + \sum_{j=1}^M a_j \Phi(\|x - x_j\|) \quad (\text{A2.1})$$

where Φ is the radial basis function, being $\| \cdot \|$ the Euclidian norm; $p(x)$ is a monomial basis $\{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_n\}$, formed of a number of monomials of degree of 1 equal to the data dimension (n) and a monomial of degree of 0, being $b = \{b_0, b_1, \dots, b_d\}$ the coefficients of these monomials.

The RBF coefficients a_j and the monomial coefficients b are obtained by enforcing the interpolation constraints $RBF(x_i) = f_i$.

There are several expressions for radial basis functions (linear, cubic, Gaussian, multiquadric), some of them containing a shape parameter that plays an important role for the accuracy of the interpolation method. Rippa (1999) has proposed an algorithm for choosing an optimal value of the shape parameter by minimizing a cost function that imitates the error between the radial interpolant and the unknown function $f(x)$. This cost function collects the errors for a sequence of partial fits to the data: $E = (E_1, \dots, E_M)^T$, where E_k is defined as the error between the function f_k in the point x_k and the estimated value by the RBF function calculated removing the point x_k from the original data set.

In the implementation of the RBF interpolation technique in the wind turbine loads series reconstruction, we have M points 8-dimensional $D_j = \{H_{si}, T_{mi}, SWL_i, \theta_{Waves\ i}, U_{Tidal\ i}, \theta_{Tidal\ i}, V_{1-hour\ i}, \theta_{Windi}\}; j=1, \dots, M$, corresponding to the M cases selected by MDA algorithm and the associated (real) forces obtained by the application of the specific formulation to evaluate the environmental forces acting on the wind turbine (i.e, the total horizontal and vertical force $F_{u,j}$ and $F_{v,j}$, and the total horizontal and vertical momentum $M_{u,j}$ and $M_{v,j}$).

Therefore, the aim of the RBF application is the evaluation of the interpolation function of the forces acting on the wind turbine decomposed in the components x - and y -, RBF_{Fu} and RBF_{Fv} , respectively

In order to calculate the interpolation functions, the variables that define the process are normalized by means a lineal transformation which scale the values between 0 and 1. Therefore

each initial situation is defined as $X_i = \{H_{si}, T_{mi}, SWL_i, \theta_{Waves\ i}, U_{Tidal\ i}, \theta_{Tidal\ i}, V_{1-hour\ i}, \theta_{Windi}\}$; $i=1, \dots, N$, while each selected case, where the real forces are available, is expressed as $D_j = \{H_{sj}, T_{mj}, SWL_j, \theta_{Waves\ j}, U_{Tidal\ j}, \theta_{Tidal\ j}, V_{1-hour\ j}, \theta_{Windi}\}$; $j=1, \dots, M$

The interpolation function is calculated by means this expression:

$$RBF(X_i) = p(X_i) + \sum_{j=1}^M a_j \Phi(\|X_i - D_j\|) \quad (A2.2)$$

where $p(X_i) = b_0 + b_1 H_i + b_2 T_{mi} + b_3 SWL_i + b_4 \theta_{wi} + b_5 U_{ti} + b_6 \theta_{Uti} + b_7 V_{1hi} + b_8 \theta_{windi}$ and Φ is a gaussian function with a shape parameter c .

$$\Phi(\|X_i - D_j\|) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|X_i - D_j\|^2}{2c^2}\right) \quad (A2.3)$$

The optimal shape parameter is estimated by Rippa algorithm. The coefficients $b_l = [b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5, b_6, b_7, b_8]^T$ of the monomials and the coefficients $a_j = [a_1, \dots, a_M]^T$ of the radial basis functions are obtained by the interpolation conditions:

$$RBF(D_j) = f_j(D_j) = D_{p,j}; \quad j = 1, \dots, M \quad (A2.4)$$

where the real functions f_j are defined by the parameters $\{F_h\}, \{F_v\}, \{M_u\}$ or $\{M_v\}$ obtained, corresponding to the selected sea states by MDA algorithm D_j .

Therefore, loads over the wind turbine are reconstructed to the entire period of data by means the RBF functions calculated for each calculated parameter. These functions are defined as:

$$F_{u,i} = RBF_{Fu}(\{D_j, F_{u,j}(j=1, \dots, M)\}, X_i); i=1, \dots, N \quad (\text{A2.5})$$

$$F_{v,i} = RBF_{Fv}(\{D_j, F_{v,j}(j=1, \dots, M)\}, X_i); i=1, \dots, N \quad (\text{A2.6})$$

$$M_{u,i} = RBF_{Mu}(\{D_j, M_{h,j}(j=1, \dots, M)\}, X_i); i=1, \dots, N \quad (\text{A2.7})$$

$$M_{v,i} = RBF_{Mv}(\{D_j, M_{v,j}(j=1, \dots, M)\}, X_i); i=1, \dots, N \quad (\text{A2.8})$$

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TABLE CAPTIONS

Table 2. The normalized root mean square error and the correlation coefficient of F_u (X component) and F_v (Y component)

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Diagram of the methodology

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the methodology proposed

Figure 3. Location of the case study.

Figure 4. Comparison of KMA (k-means), SOM (Self-Organizing Maps) and MDA (Maximum dissimilarity) algorithms

Figure 5. Time series of H_s , T_p , θ (wave direction), SWL, Tidal Current (in its components X and Y) and Wind (in its components X and Y) at the wind turbine location (grey line), the cases selected by MDA algorithm, $M=1,50$ red points, $M=51,100$ green points and $M=101,200$ yellow points.

Figure 6. Distribution of cases selected by MDA algorithm ($M=1,50$ red points, $M=51,100$ green points and $M=101,200$ yellow points).

Figure 7. Loads on a wind turbine

Figure 8. Thrust force on the turbine

Figure 9. Scatter plot of the time series (calculated vs. reconstructed) of F_u (X component) and F_v (Y component) considering $M=75$, $M=200$ and $M=1000$

Figure 10. Time series calculated (in black) and the time series reconstructed considering $M=200$ cases (in orange) and $M=1000$ cases (in red) of parameters F_u (X component) and F_v (Y component)

Figure 11. Peak Over Threshold (POT) distribution of the module of forces at the wind turbine (95% confidence intervals in dashed lines)

Figure 12. Roses of spatial distribution of wind (upper left rose), wave (upper central rose), currents (upper right rose) and total force magnitude (lower rose).

Figure 13. Probabilistic roses of the different components of forces acting on a wind turbine, 1992 (waves component: upper left panel, wind component: upper right panel, currents component: lower left panel and total force (sum of the three components): lower right panel).

Figure 14. Probabilistic roses for the total force acting upon a wind turbine, 1999 (left panel), 2000 (central panel) and 2001(right panel)

TABLE CAPTIONS

	Fu					Fv				
	MDA=75	MDA=200	MDA=500	MDA=750	MDA=1000	MDA=75	MDA=200	MDA=500	MDA=750	MDA=1000
NRMSE	0.0367	0.0276	0.0165	0.0150	0.0138	0.0531	0.0375	0.0220	0.0183	0.0163
ρ	0.9389	0.9635	0.9865	0.9887	0.9905	0.8875	0.9381	0.9773	0.9840	0.9873

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